

Website

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February-2022

Achieving wider uptake of water-sm art solutions

Project number: 869283

Project duration: May 2020 – April 2024

H2020-SC5-2019-2

WWW.WIDER-UPTAKE.EU

D7.5 – Public

Website

VERSION

02

DATE

15-February-2022

ABSTRACT

The project website has been established for presentation and dissemination of the project and its deliverables. The address is www.wider-uptake.eu.

In addition, two national websites for national dissemination and communication around the project have already been created, one in Italy: <https://wideruptake.unipa.it/> and one in Czech Republic: <https://tvp.vscht.cz/research/projects-grants/54926> (in English) and https://tvp.vscht.cz/veda-a-vyzkum/projekty/54923?ecrof&jazyk=cs#novinka_detail (in Czech).

A “members-only” area has been established in the Microsoft Platform Teams as a file exchange platform to facilitate internal communication and exchange of data, results, reports and software tools.

As a mean of verification, this document presents an overview of the website statistics from 1st of May 2020 to 28th October 2020.

Updates after the project review in February 2022:

- Links to newsletter subscription and previous newsletters are available on the front page.
- List of publications is updated.
- The menu structure is updated in order to enhance the focus on deliverables and activities in the demo cases.

Plans for further improvements:

Further improve the content and structure on the webpage with increased focus on innovations and results from the demonstration cases and cross cutting work packages.

KEYWORDS

Communication, website.

DELIVERABLE ID

D7.5

WORK PACKAGE

WP7

PLANNED DELIVERY DATE

15-February-2020

AUTHORSHIP AND APPROVAL INFORMATION

LEAD BENEFICIARY

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Website statistics 1st May – 28th October 2020

Number of page views

The table below shows the number of page views, number of unique page views, average time per page, number of entrances, escape rates and percentage of exits for each of the pages of the main website of WIDER UPTAKE (www.wider-uptake.eu) during the period 1st May – 28th October 2020.

Side	Sidevisninger	Unike sidevisninger	Gj.sn. tid på side	Innganger	Fluktfrekvens	% Utgang
	2 075 % av summen: 0,18 % (1 571 187)	1 429 % av summen: 0,11 % (1 297 690)	00:01:28 Gj.sn. for datoavslaget: 00:01:27 (0,99 %)	495 % av summen: 0,07 % (787 723)	48,48 % Gj.sn. for datoavslaget: 70,88 % (-91,11 %)	24,43 % Gj.sn. for datoavslaget: 48,23 % (-49,84 %)
1. /projectweb/wider-uptake/	620 (29,88 %)	455 (31,84 %)	00:02:28	386 (77,98 %)	48,19 %	40,00 %
2. /projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/	228 (10,99 %)	153 (10,71 %)	00:01:00	20 (4,04 %)	45,00 %	18,86 %
3. /projectweb/wider-uptake/partners/	175 (8,43 %)	137 (9,59 %)	00:01:58	18 (3,64 %)	55,56 %	31,43 %
4. /projectweb/wider-uptake/news/	148 (7,13 %)	91 (6,37 %)	00:00:23	2 (0,40 %)	0,00 %	8,11 %
5. /projectweb/wider-uptake/events/	121 (5,83 %)	81 (5,67 %)	00:00:26	7 (1,41 %)	42,86 %	7,44 %
6. /projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/case-studies/	107 (5,16 %)	82 (5,74 %)	00:01:57	22 (4,44 %)	68,18 %	37,38 %
7. /projectweb/wider-uptake/contacts/	86 (4,14 %)	76 (5,32 %)	00:01:10	7 (1,41 %)	71,43 %	39,53 %
8. /projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/work-package-descriptions/	59 (2,84 %)	42 (2,94 %)	00:00:53	4 (0,81 %)	0,00 %	13,56 %
9. /projectweb/wider-uptake/news/virtual-kick-off-18.06.2020/	56 (2,70 %)	42 (2,94 %)	00:02:53	6 (1,21 %)	33,33 %	26,79 %
10. /projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/communities-of-practice/	41 (1,98 %)	34 (2,38 %)	00:00:24	3 (0,61 %)	66,67 %	21,95 %
11. /projectweb/wider-uptake/news/on-site-inspection/	36 (1,73 %)	29 (2,03 %)	00:01:05	8 (1,62 %)	25,00 %	16,67 %
12. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/case-studies_319342/?epi editmode=true	33 (1,59 %)	3 (0,21 %)	00:00:44	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %
13. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do_318846/?epieditmode=tru e	32 (1,54 %)	5 (0,35 %)	00:00:41	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %
14. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/news_318847/?epieditmode=true	25 (1,20 %)	5 (0,35 %)	00:00:31	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %
15. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/partners_318938/?epieditmode=true	25 (1,20 %)	8 (0,56 %)	00:01:38	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	8,00 %
16. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/contacts_318939/?epieditmode=true	19 (0,92 %)	5 (0,35 %)	00:01:42	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	5,26 %
17. /projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/project-impacts/	17 (0,82 %)	13 (0,91 %)	00:00:03	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	5,88 %
18. /projectweb/wider-uptake/events/kick-off-june-2020/	16 (0,77 %)	10 (0,70 %)	00:00:10	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	12,50 %
19. /projectweb/wider-uptake/news/wider-uptake-virtual-kick-off-18.06.2020/	16 (0,77 %)	7 (0,49 %)	00:03:30	4 (0,81 %)	50,00 %	31,25 %
20. /projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/meet-the-team/	16 (0,77 %)	13 (0,91 %)	00:00:07	1 (0,20 %)	0,00 %	6,25 %
21. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/events_318937/?epieditmode=true	15 (0,72 %)	5 (0,35 %)	00:01:14	1 (0,20 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %
22. /projectweb/wider-uptake/news/launch-day-in-palermo/	12 (0,58 %)	10 (0,70 %)	00:07:55	1 (0,20 %)	100,00 %	33,33 %
23. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/what-we-do/work-package-description s_319341/?epieditmode=true	10 (0,48 %)	4 (0,28 %)	00:01:06	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %
24. /pages/ui/cms/content/projectweb/wider-uptake/news/wider-uptake-virtual-kick-off-18. 06.2020_320188/?epieditmode=true	8 (0,39 %)	3 (0,21 %)	00:03:39	0 (0,00 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %
25. /projectweb/wider-uptake/sok/?root=318831	8 (0,39 %)	7 (0,49 %)	00:00:09	1 (0,20 %)	0,00 %	0,00 %

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Revision of the webpage in February 2022

The webpage has been updated after the project review in February 2022:

- Links to newsletter subscription and previous newsletters are available on the front page.
- List of publications is updated.
- The menu structure is updated in order to enhance the focus on deliverables and activities in the demo cases. All the basic project information has been collected under the heading "About us".

The webpage will be further improved in 2022 with regards to layout and structure of the webpage. During the second reporting period, the content will be further developed with increased focus on innovations and results from the demonstration cases and cross cutting work packages.

Figure 1: Layout of the original webpage

Figure 2: Layout of revised webpage 15th February 2022